

ASSESSMENT OF SELF-LEARNING MODULE OF GRADE 10 ENGLISH OF BATANGAS STATE UNIVERSITY INTEGRATED SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

The researchers assessed the self-learning module of Grade 10 English to gauge the perception of the students upon using it. The assessment of the Self-learning Module will benefit significant pedagogical aspects, curriculum, learning environment and policy. Specifically, the study assessed the SLM of Grade 10 English in terms of content, usefulness, accuracy, presentation and organization, physical quality and inclusivity; identified the problems encountered by the respondents in using the SLM and prepared a supplementary module for English 10 based on the findings. Quantitative descriptive research was used in this study to meet its main purpose. On the other hand, a qualitative research design was also used for the two open ended questions to determine how the students cope with the problems encountered. The instrument used for gathering data for the research was a survey questionnaire. The researchers designed the questionnaire as the primary tool to utilized to gather relevant information for the study. The subjects of the study were 150 Grade 10 students from the Integrated School at Batangas State University-Pablo Borbon Campus for the school year 2020-2021. For interpretation, the researchers used statistical instruments such as weighted and composite mean, as well as ranking. Results of the study showed that the assessed SLM is useful and has relevant content, displays accuracy, proper presentation and organization, good physical quality, and promotes inclusivity. The findings also revealed that although the SLM was of good quality based on the variables in which it was assessed, the students still encountered problems that may have affected their learning process. Those who were affected said they experienced confusion and difficulty of understanding, loss of interest/motivation, slowed down learning pace, and declining mental health. In terms of overcoming these problems, respondents stated that they overcame problems by asking for guidance, internet browsing, time management, and positive thinking. From the overall results of the study, the self-learning module is still considered as a good learning material. After the analysis, a supplementary module was prepared. The output consisted of other reference materials for each lesson, while also providing various activities that would help students enrich their English language skills. Likewise, the researchers aligned the material with the Grade 10 English syllabus and anchored the content based on the outcome of the study.

Keywords: SLM, assessment, distance learning, learning materials, English language learning.